
Optical absorption improvement of PANI/MnFe₂O₄/ZnO photocatalyst under visible light irradiation

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Abstract ZnO as a promising photocatalyst has gained main attention for degradation of organic pollutants from water environments. However, the main drawback of ZnO is the relatively low photocatalytic activity, because of high recombination rate of photoexcited electron-hole pairs that restrict its potential applications. Herein, novel magnetic photocatalyst of PANI/MnFe₂O₄/ZnO was synthesized by in situ oxidative polymerization of aniline in the presence of MnFe₂O₄ as magnetic component and ZnO as photoactive component. The physicochemical properties of synthesized sample was characterized by using X-ray diffraction (XRD), Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR), field emission scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM) and UV-vis spectroscopy. The catalytic activity of the as prepared PANI/MnFe₂O₄/ZnO as photocatalyst was investigated by degradation of methyl orange (MO) as a model contaminant in aqueous solution under visible light irradiation. The obtained results indicated that the as prepared PANI/MnFe₂O₄/ZnO show highly enhanced photocatalytic activity for degradation of MO as compared with the parent materials, because of the synergistic effect among ZnO, MnFe₂O₄ and PANI. Moreover, the magnetic photocatalyst of PANI/MnFe₂O₄/ZnO can be easily separated from the aqueous solution by an external magnet and reused for several cycles.

Keywords Polyaniline; Magnetically separable; visible light; Photocatalyst; ZnO

1. Introduction

Azo dyes used in textile and food industries are their important sources of the environmental contaminations due to their non-biodegradability and high toxicity and carcinogenic effects on humans [1, 2]. One of this class of dyes, Methyl Orange (MO) is a water-soluble azo dye (Fig. 1), widely used in the textile, printing, paper manufacturing, pharmaceutical and food industries and metabolizes into aromatic amines by intestinal microorganisms which can enter the body through ingestion and make intestinal cancer. Semiconductor research has demonstrated the main application in areas such as hydrogen production through photocatalytic water splitting [3, 4], dye sensitized solar cells [5] and photocatalytic treatment of harmful organics from air and water [6]. Among these investigations, developing of efficient visible light responsive photocatalysts for environmental remediation has become the main area in photocatalysis research because of the usage of solar light [7-9]. ZnO with a wideband gap ($E_g = 3.37$ eV) is one of the most important photocatalysts, which has been widely used in photocatalytic degradation of organic pollutants [10-12]. However, for the actual applications, traditional ZnO photocatalysts are usually not suitable due to the inconvenient and expensive separation [13], high photocorrosion [14], and low quantum efficiency resulted from its wide band gap and the rapid recombination of photo-generated carriers [15]. Therefore, it is a great challenge to make ZnO-based photocatalysis active under visible light. In this regard, the modified ZnO-based photocatalysis with conducting polymers such as PANI can respond to visible light region effectively [16-18]. PANI

has shown high absorption coefficient in the visible light range and high mobility of charge carriers. Under the irradiation of visible light, PANI not only is an electron donor but also itself is an excellent hole acceptor [19–21]. Moreover, from the practical view the ZnO-based photocatalysis coupled with conducting polymers are difficult to separate and recover from aqueous solution. However, the magnetic component used is often unstable in acidic medium and may interact with substrates. In this regard, MnFe_2O_4 as the important magnetic materials have been utilized with photocatalysts and allowing easy separation of the photocatalysts from the liquid after the photocatalytic process [22,23]. In this study, we provide a simple method to synthesize the magnetically recyclable PANI/ MnFe_2O_4 /ZnO photocatalyst by in situ oxidative polymerization method. Moreover, under visible light irradiation both of pure MnFe_2O_4 and PANI exhibit poor photocatalytic activity and pure ZnO shows a little higher photocatalytic activity. However, when PANI was combined with MnFe_2O_4 and PANI, the resulting compound show an enhanced photocatalytic activity for degradation of Methyl orange (MO) under visible light. Also, the stability and reusability of PANI/ MnFe_2O_4 /ZnO photocatalyst was also examined. This study could greatly promote the potential applications of magnetic ZnO-based photocatalysts in eliminating hazardous contaminants.

Figure 1: The chemical structure of Methyl orange

2. Experimental

2.1. Materials

Methyl orange, aniline, nitric acid, ammonium peroxydisulfate, $\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Mn}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, ZnO and NaOH were purchased from Merck Company.

2.2. Instrumentation

The prepared samples were characterized by using XRD (Holland Philips Xpert, X-ray diffractometer with Cu-K α radiation), field emission scanning electron microscopy and energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (FE-SEM, EDX, Vega 2 Tscan), a Fourier transform infrared spectrometer (JASCO FTIR-4200) and UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Shimadzu-2550).

2.3. Synthesis of MnFe_2O_4

For preparation of the MnFe_2O_4 , 4.4 g $\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and 0.89 g $\text{Mn}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ were dissolved in 50 mL EtOH solution. Then 15 mL of the NaOH 4M solution was added dropwise into the above solution. After stirring the mixture for 3 h at 30 °C, the product was separated, washed with distilled water several times and dried at 60 °C. Then heat treatment of the product was carried out at 900 °C for 2 h.

2.4. Synthesis of PANI/ MnFe_2O_4 /ZnO photocatalyst

The PANI/ MnFe_2O_4 /ZnO sample was prepared by in situ polymerization of aniline on the surface of the MnFe_2O_4 and ZnO samples that reported previously [24]. In this procedure, 10 mL of 0.1 M aniline, 10 mL of 0.125 ammonium peroxydisulfate and 30 mL of 0.1 M nitric acid solutions were added to 0.1g of synthesized MnFe_2O_4 and 0.25g of ZnO at room temperature. Then, the mixture was stirred during the polymerization of aniline, which was completed within 24 h. Finally, the prepared sample PANI/ MnFe_2O_4 /ZnO was dried at 60°C.

2.5. The photocatalytic experiments

In this study the dye MO solution was chosen as an environmental pollutant model. The disappearance of the peaks at $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 466$ nm was chosen for monitoring of dye decolorization for MO solution. In each experiment, 0.10 g of the PANI/ MnFe_2O_4 /ZnO as photocatalyst was added in 100 mL to the above solution with a V/V ratio of 1:1. Air was blown into the reaction vessel by an aquarium pump to maintain the solution saturated with oxygen. In this research, a 100W filament tungsten lamp was used as the visible light source. The degree of photodecolorization(X), as a function of time, is given by Eq. (1)

$$X = \frac{C_0 - C_t}{C_0} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

Where C_0 is the initial concentration of dye, and C_t is the concentration of dye at time t . The progress of photocatalytic decolorization was measured by UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Shimadzu UV-2550).

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Characterization of PANI/MnFe₂O₄/ZnO

The Fourier transform infrared (FT-IR) spectra of the as-synthesized PANI/MnFe₂O₄/ZnO sample in Fig.2 demonstrated two peaks at 3404 and 1631 cm⁻¹ that are attributed to the absorbed water molecules on the surface of the sample. Also, the two peaks at 560 and 425 cm⁻¹ are attributed to the vibrations of Zn-O and Fe-O bonds, respectively [25].

Figure 2: FT-IR spectrum of (a) MnFe₂O₄, (b) PANI/MnFe₂O₄ and (c) PANI/MnFe₂O₄/ZnO

The XRD patterns of ZnO, MnFe₂O₄ and PANI/MnFe₂O₄/ZnO are shown in Fig.3. The XRD patterns of ZnO and MnFe₂O₄ are in accordance with reported literature [26, 27]. The magnetic sample of PANI/MnFe₂O₄/ZnO shows the characteristic peaks of both ZnO and MnFe₂O₄. However, it could be noticed that the characteristic diffraction peak of MnFe₂O₄ in the PANI/MnFe₂O₄/ZnO was weak, which could be attributed to the low amount of the MnFe₂O₄ used in the synthesis of PANI/MnFe₂O₄/ZnO. The peaks corresponding to polyaniline are not detected, indicating that polyaniline was amorphous in the synthesized PANI/MnFe₂O₄/ZnO. No peak for another crystal phase is detected, indicating that there is no crystal phase impurity in the obtained sample.

Figure 3: XRD curve of PANI/MnFe₂O₄/ZnO

The morphologies of MnFe_2O_4 , and $\text{PANI}/\text{MnFe}_2\text{O}_4/\text{ZnO}$ were studied by SEM. The SEM images of the $\text{PANI}/\text{MnFe}_2\text{O}_4/\text{ZnO}$ sample are shown in Fig.4. Comparing the morphology of $\text{PANI}/\text{MnFe}_2\text{O}_4/\text{ZnO}$ with that of MnFe_2O_4 , it clearly suggests that the introduction of PANI and MnFe_2O_4 is of great importance for obtaining a novel material. As expected, the microspheres of PANI are uniformly spherical which can be seen from SEM images of the $\text{PANI}/\text{MnFe}_2\text{O}_4/\text{ZnO}$ sample.

Figure 4: SEM images of pure MnFe_2O_4 (a) & (b) $\text{PANI}/\text{MnFe}_2\text{O}_4/\text{ZnO}$ (c) & (d)

3.2. Photocatalytic degradation of MO over MnFe_2O_4 , $\text{PANI}/\text{MnFe}_2\text{O}_4$ and $\text{PANI}/\text{MnFe}_2\text{O}_4/\text{ZnO}$ samples

To evaluate activity of the prepared $\text{PANI}/\text{MnFe}_2\text{O}_4/\text{ZnO}$, the degradation of MO under visible light irradiation was considered. When photocatalyst absorbs visible radiation, it will produce pair of electrons and holes. These charge carriers can recombine, or the holes can be scavenged by oxidizing species and electrons by reducible species in the solution, which finally, lead to the destruction of many organic pollutants. The radicals are formed by scavenging of electrons and holes via molecular oxygen and water [28]. The active species generated by photo-irradiation will attack the pollutant, if this is in the very close vicinity of the photocatalyst. Generally, the photocatalytic kinetic of dye solution can be described by the Eq. (2) [29].

$$\ln(C_0/C_t) = k_{app} t \quad (2)$$

Where C_0 is the concentrations of dye solution, C_t is the concentration of dye solution at time t and k_{app} is the apparent rate constant. Generally, linear correlation of $\ln(C_0/C_t)$ versus time plot suggests a pseudo first order reaction. The plot of $\ln(C_0/C_t)$ versus time for the $\text{PANI}/\text{MnFe}_2\text{O}_4/\text{ZnO}$, $\text{PANI}/\text{MnFe}_2\text{O}_4$ and MnFe_2O_4 samples were presented in Fig. 6. The rate constant for the $\text{PANI}/\text{MnFe}_2\text{O}_4/\text{ZnO}$, $\text{PANI}/\text{MnFe}_2\text{O}_4$ and MnFe_2O_4 samples was obtained as 0.012, 0.006 and 0.0055 min^{-1} , respectively.

Figure 5: Photodecolorization of MO as a function of the irradiation time for (a) $MnFe_2O_4$, (b) $PANI/MnFe_2O_4$ and (c) $PANI/MnFe_2O_4/ZnO$

Figure 6: Photocatalytic kinetic of MO solution for (a) $MnFe_2O_4$, (b) $PANI/MnFe_2O_4$ and (c) $PANI/MnFe_2O_4/ZnO$

3.3. Mechanism of photocatalytic activity

The mechanism of photocatalytic MO degradation over $PANI/MnFe_2O_4/ZnO$ under visible light is presented in Fig. 6. When irradiated under visible light, PANI can absorb visible light to induce the transitions $\pi \rightarrow$ polaron and polaron $\rightarrow \pi^*$, delivering the excited-state electrons of the highest unoccupied molecular orbital (HOMO) to the lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (LUMO). On the basis of the synergistic effect, the excited-state electrons in the LUMO of PANI molecules can migrate into the CB of ZnO subsequently, they transfer to the surface of ZnO and react with water to produce superoxide radical, which could oxidize the organic molecules. As a photosensitizer, PANI makes wonderful contributions to the still highly photocatalytic activity under visible light which attribute to that hydroxyl radicals and superoxide anions were produced by them, and the most important is that $\bullet OH$ would oxidize the organic dyes [30].

4. Conclusion

In summary, $PANI/MnFe_2O_4/ZnO$ photocatalyst are prepared by in situ oxidative polymerization of aniline in the presence of $MnFe_2O_4$ and ZnO and for the first time which has enhanced photocatalytic activity under visible light irradiation and can be separated using an external magnet. The photocatalytic degradation experiments demonstrate

that the as-prepared catalyst displayed a high photocatalytic activity toward MO under visible light irradiation with their own optimum experimental condition.

Acknowledgements

We are grateful to Payame Noor University for its financial support.

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